

Navigating Self-Reliance Through Sustainable Agricultural Transformation in India with Reference to ATMANIRBHAR BHARAT

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Abstract: Sustainable agriculture, also known as Regenerative Agriculture, is an agricultural practice that focuses on producing crops and livestock with minimal environmental impact. This form of agriculture tends to strike a balance between food production and the preservation of the ecological health of the environment. India has been growing crops using environmentally compatible indigenous farming techniques traditionally. In recent times, owing to a host of benefits, be it economical, ecological as well as health the Government of India is stressing a lot on adoption of sustainable agriculture as a standard farming practice in the country. Fulfillment of these goals will lead to Atmanirbhar Kisan (self-reliant farmers) which will lead to development of Atmanirbhar Krishi (Self-reliant agriculture) and ultimately the long cherished dream of Atmanirbhar Bharat or a Self-reliant India; a happy and progressive New India of the 21st century would be a reality.

Keywords: Sustainable Agriculture, Atmanirbhar Bharat, Self-Reliant, ecological, Agriculture.

Introduction

Sustainable Agriculture in the present-day context has become a necessary condition to realize the goal of Sustainable Development, which the majority of the countries in the world is striving hard to achieve. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the UNO, “Sustainable agriculture is the successful management of resources for agriculture to satisfy changing human needs while maintaining or enhancing the quality of environment and conserving natural resources”. Sustainable Agriculture lays emphasis on maintaining an agriculture growth rate, which can meet the demand for food of all living beings without draining the basic resources.

“Agriculture is the backbone of the Indian economy;” the words spoken by the father of the Nation seems to be true even in the eve of 75th year of India’s independence. The agricultural sector’s contribution accounts for 18.8 percent of the country’s Gross Value Added (GVA) for the year 2021-22 (at current prices) and provides employment to about 54.6 percent of the total workforce either directly or indirectly¹. The Green Revolution started in the 1960s has been instrumental in transforming India from a food deficient state to a self sufficient nation in food grain production by the early 1970s. But the excessive use of synthetic fertilizers, heavy chemicals, pesticides etc in the fields as per green revolution initiatives has resulted in eventual degradation of the quality of soil, loss of productivity of soil, etc., which led to a decrease in agricultural production and eventually a fall in farmers’ income which making them vulnerable to a vicious cycle of debt. To tide over this ever-rising crisis, Sustainable Agriculture seems to be the best solution in the present context.

With the prevalence of traditional farming techniques involving intercropping, mulching, use of natural inputs like cow dung, green manure and natural pesticides, integration of crops and livestock rearing etc carried out since centuries and passed down from generation to generation and also a culture where an Indian farmer loves mother nature and respects, worships and protects his farmlands as

his mother, the ethos of Sustainable Agriculture is deeply rooted in the agricultural practices of India. Owing to a host of benefits like producing high nutritional quality food along with nurturing the health and regenerating the productive quality of the soil which sustainable agriculture offers the Government of India has been putting a lot of stress on promoting scientific based sustainable agriculture as a standard agricultural practice in the country. The development of Sustainable Agriculture has been enshrined in the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan (Self –reliant India or self- sufficient India Mission) launched by the honorable Prime Minister Narendra Modi on May 12 ,2020. A huge chunk of budgetary allocations in the consecutive years following the announcement of the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan has been devoted towards promoting sustainable agriculture to make Atmanirbhar Krishi (self-reliant India) which would be a growth engine leading towards Atmanirbhar Bharat (self-reliant India) in order to make the 21st century belong to India.

Literature Review

Patidar, S and Patidar, H. (2015) devoted their study on evaluating the perceptions of farmers towards organic cultivation as a form of sustainable agricultural practice in context of Khargone district of Madhya Pradesh in their research article entitled “A Study of Perception of Farmers towards Organic Farming”. The results shows that the positive perception of farmers towards organic farming is related to several factors like their age, educational background, farm size, social factors etc as the drivers of farmers adopting a positive behavior towards organic farming. The study suggests that measures like provision of easy and cheap credit facilities, providing training to farmers on organic farming etc if undertaken by government will further give an impetus towards growth of organic farming in the near future.

Bist, J. (2020) in his research article titled ‘Indian Agriculture: Policies for Sustainable Transformation’ analyzed various schemes launched by the government of India like National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture (NMSA), the Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchayee Yojana (PMKSY), Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY)etc. Different dimensions of the above-mentioned schemes like benefits it offers, various constraints in its implementations etc. are studied in details.

The Government of India Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers welfare Department of Agriculture, Cooperation & Farmers welfare (2020) published a report named Inspiring Stories of Progressive Women Farmers which have a success story of Ms. Nabanita Das of Jorhat as a progressive organic farmer of Assam in an article “Journey of Nurse to become a Farmer”. The article is based upon the achievements of Ms. Nabanita Das of Jorhat as progressive organic farmer and agripreneur. She has been practicing organic farming from many years and has been successful in opening an organic farm named “Nabanita Organic Farm.” Undertaking scientific organic farming techniques of production, she had converted her previous typical mono cropped rice land by adopting sunken bed method into a model flower crop-based farming system and had widened her scope of production by including fish pond, animal husbandry etc. At present her farm has become a small agri hub with production of wide varieties of flowers (Anthurium, Gerbera etc), rice (Keteki Joha, Kunkuni Joha, and Kola Joha etc), eggs, milk, goatery etc. Her success story serves as a flame of inspiration for many farmers to adopt a positive behavior towards organic farming as a sustainable form of agriculture in the future.

Vala, Y.B. and Patel, C.K. (2021) in their research article titled 'Low-Cost Natural Farming – A Step towards Atmanirbhar Bharat' analyzed the concept of Natural Farming as a part of sustainable agriculture. The article highlighted the central pillars of natural farming, role of natural farming towards Atmanirbhar Bharat, various government initiatives towards promotion of natural farming and the farmer's feedback after adoption of natural farming techniques.

Objectives Of the Study

1. Examining the importance of Sustainable Agriculture with reference to Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan
2. Examining the effectiveness of different schemes towards the promotion of Sustainable Agriculture in India.
3. Providing necessary suggestions to overcome the challenges.

Research Methodology

This study type is a conceptual study which is based on secondary source of data. Secondary source of data is used to highlight the conceptual analysis and the review of literature. The sources of secondary data are taken from various reports on sustainable agriculture released by government agencies like Ministry of Agriculture, Annual report on agriculture, Indian budget 2023 report etc. In addition to these few research articles published in a number of journals had been taken help of.

Discussion

Importance Of Sustainable Agriculture for Atmanirbhar Bharat-

1. Better Climate Resilient Crops: As sustainable agricultural practices involve the use of natural inputs for agriculture like cow dung, green manure, neem based pesticides etc it has been seen that crops grown using these inputs seems to offer better resilience in the face of extreme climatic events like acute and frequent droughts, floods, menace of locust attacks etc. For example, in the state of Andhra Pradesh, during the advent of the Pethai and the Titli cyclones in the year 2018, the crops cultivated through natural farming showed greater resilience to the winds than conventional crops. This highlights the potential of sustainable farming as it reduces the fear of crop failure. This helps in making India achieve atmanirbharta (self sufficiency) in agricultural production.

2. Increase In Farmers' Income: Sustainable agricultural practices offer the farmers with an option of reduced cost of agricultural inputs as the green revolution-based initiatives incurs huge costs for the farmers. With the ever increasing demand for organic food products globally in the current times, farmers can reap the benefits of a ready market for their organically grown crops and sell them at a higher price. Mixed farming techniques seems to offer a steady flow of income for the farmer all round the year as different crops mature in varied seasons of the year and livestock in addition to crops ensures more income for the farmer. Reduction in agricultural production costs in combination with an increased income for the farmers seems to improve the economic and social status of the farmers making them Atmanirbhar. Thus Atmanirbhar Kisan or self reliant or self sufficient farmers will eventually lead the country towards self sufficiency.

3. Ensures Food Security: Organically grown crops are of high nutritional quality and does not have any adverse effects upon human health as posed by those crops grown using synthetic fertilizers, heavy chemicals, insecticides, and pesticides etc. Apart from this the risk of crop failure in case of organically grown crops is less as they have high resilience capacity against any climatic event like

droughts, floods, locusts attacks etc. Thus scientific based sustainable agricultural practices could lead to increase in agricultural production of the country fulfilling the principle of Atmanirbhar Bharat.

4. Increase In Export Earnings: It has been estimated that the global market for organic food was valued at \$187,485.6 million in 2020 and is expected to reach \$860,625.7 million by 2031, registering a CAGR of 14.9 percent from 2022 to 2031². It offers an ample opportunity for countries like India which have been blessed in bounty by nature to grow a large number of crops; to take up sustainable agriculture as a standard agricultural practice and reap the benefits of a widening global market for organic products. Rise in exports of organic products will bring in precious foreign exchange in the form of export earnings to the country and help in correcting the BOP disequilibrium.

5. Protection of the Environment: The extensive use of synthetic pesticides, chemical fertilizers etc as a part of green revolution initiatives has resulted in several undesirable environmental impacts like loss of fertility of soil, reduction of agricultural production, loss of bio diversity etc. But the ethos of environmental sustainability seems to be fulfilled by adopting sustainable agriculture as a standard agricultural practice in India. Use of natural inputs in agriculture like vermicompost, natural pesticides etc enhances the quality of soil and restores its regenerative capacity. Employing techniques like sprinkle & drip irrigation results in about 60 percent reduction in water usage. Thus, sustainable agriculture ensures protection of natural resources for the future generations in order to meet their ability to satisfy their food and fiber demands.

Chief Government Program towards Sustainable Agriculture

National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture (NMSA): A flagship program of the Central government which was first enshrined as one of the eight missions outlined under the National Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC). It became operational in the year 2014-15 and is devoted towards fulfilling the objective of promoting sustainable agriculture and enhances agricultural productivity across the country. The mission aims at, "making agriculture more productive, sustainable, and remunerative and climate resilient by promoting location specific integrated/composite farming systems; soil and moisture conservation measures; comprehensive soil management; efficient water management practices and mainstreaming rainfed technologies". The schemes under NMSA are:

- i) **Rainfed Area Development (RAD):** This scheme is launched to promote integrated farming practices which involves mixed farming techniques along with horticulture, fisheries and livestock etc in rainfed areas of the country with an aim to improve farmers' incomes and mitigate the impacts of natural calamities like flood, droughts etc. The scheme is important from the fact that out of 140.1 million hectares (mha) of cultivated land about 71.7 mha is rainfed³. This scheme is devoted towards creation and development of common property resources, facilities like grain banks, biomass shredders, fodder bank etc in the rainfed areas. A fund of Rs 3100 cr has been allocated for this scheme. As per NMSA report area covered under RAD scheme has increased from 35,543.1 hectare in the year 2015-16 to about 45,270.5 hectare in the year 2019-20.
- ii) **Sub-Mission on Agro forestry (SMAF):** This scheme was launched in the year 2016 to fulfill the objective of increasing plantation of trees in an integrated manner along with crop production. This mission involves plantation of

fruit bearing or timber trees on the periphery of the agricultural fields with an aim of improving the quality of soil through improving soil moisture, preventing soil erosion, enrichment of soil organic matter etc. Apart from this trees would serve as additional source of income for the marginal and small farmers across the country. As per NAMS report an allocation of about Rs 45 crores has been made towards this scheme and the area covered under this scheme increased from 373 hectare in the year 2016-2017 to about 774 hectares in 2019-2020⁴.

- iii) **Soil Health Management:** This scheme is aimed at “promoting location as well as crop specific sustainable soil health management, creating and linking soil fertility maps with macro-micro nutrient management, judicious application of fertilizers and organic farming practices” (MoAFW 2017:7). Soil Health card (SHC) is the flagship policy under this scheme which was launched in 2015. The farmers are distributed a soil health card every 3 years which gives detailed information to them regarding the status of nutrients on their land, crops best suitable to that patch of land, right nutrient dosage required etc. The main benefit of this scheme is that as a farmer knows what to grow and how to improve productivity of the soil, he can cut down his cost of inputs which results in increased income for the farmer with increased production. An amount of Rs 700 Cr has been allocated for this scheme. The distribution of SHC increased from 107.3 million farmers in 2015-17 to about 115.1 million farmers by 2021-22⁵.
- iv) **Paramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojana (PKVY):** Launched in 2015 PKVY scheme devotes itself towards encouraging organic farming on commercial basis in India by creating an organic certification system which involves both the producers and the consumers in the certification process. This system is called Participatory guarantee scheme (PGS). As per Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers welfare in the year 2019, 27.7 lakh hectare of area has been certified as organic by PGS in India. The scheme on the eve of its launched intended to convert about 2 Lakh ha of cropped area into organic farming by forming 10,000 organic clusters of 20 ha each by the year 2017-2018. As of 2022 the scheme has brought about 4.3 lakh ha under organic cultivation.
- v) **Mission Organic Value Chain Development For Northeastern Region (MOVCDNER):** It is a scheme of the central government launched in 2015 during the 12th plan period for development of organic value chains in the 8 Northeastern states. It aims to make the Northeastern states the organic hub of the country owing to the fertile soils and the favorable climatic conditions ideal for organic farming. An annual allocation of Rs 134 crore for the last five years have been made which was increased to 200 crores annually since the year 2022. The scheme entails creation of 100 FPOs or farmers Producers organization across the 8 states comprising a total land area of 50,000 hectare. The scheme provides support to complete value chain through inputs, seeds, organic certification, creation of facilities for collection, processing, aggregation, marketing and branding etc of agricultural products with an aim to improve agricultural production and farmers’ income of these states. This scheme has covered about 74,880 ha area within its framework involving about 50,000 farmers as of the year 2019-20. The target of this scheme is to cover an additional 1 lakh ha area under 200 new FPOs by the next three years.

RESULTS

- A. Owing to Atmanirbhar Bharat initiatives in Indian agriculture, the agricultural sector proved resilient to the Covid-19 shock. The annual growth rate of agriculture and allied sectors was 3.6 percent in 2020-21 which further increased to 3.9 percent in 2021-22 (Economic survey report 2021-22)
- B. Food grain production increased from 265.05 million tonnes in the year 2013-14 to a record high of 323.55 million tonnes in 2022-23 (second advance estimates). Horticulture production has increased from 280.99 million tonnes in 2014-15 to 342.33 million tonnes in 2021-22 (third advance estimates)
- C. Under Paramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojana (PKVY) 19043 clusters have been formed and an area of 3.81 lakh ha has been covered benefiting 9.52 lakh farmers. In addition, under Namami Ganga programme 123620 ha area has been covered and under natural farming 4.09 lakh ha area has been covered as per 2022 estimates.
- D. Under Mission Organic Value Chain Development in North East Region (MOVCDNER) 170 Farmer producer Companies has been formed comprising 1.55 lakh farmers and covering 1, 55,495 ha area as per 2022 estimates.

Challenges

1. As farmer's switches from conventional agriculture which involves synthetic inputs to sustainable agricultural practices which involves natural inputs, crop yield tends to drop in the initial years which tends to discourage the farmers to adopt these practices.
2. In majority of the cases, it has been observed that there is always a delay in the release of allocated funds by state governments for promotion of sustainable agriculture which creates hindrances in adoption of sustainable farming techniques by small and marginal farmers.
3. Sustainable agriculture is labour intensive in nature and it increases the workload of the farmers in preparing natural inputs for farming. These make the farmers reluctant in converting to sustainable agriculture.
4. Sustainable agriculture requires natural inputs like animal waste, cow urine, leaves of certain plants etc. However, owing to increasing mechanization the population of farm animals in villages have come down considerably leading to scarcity of animal wastes. The scarcity of natural inputs is another bottleneck towards adopting sustainable agriculture.
5. It had also been observed that there is a lack of awareness and knowledge regarding PGS certification on the part of consumers, retailers, wholesalers etc. This leads to lower price of organic produce in the markets which discourages the farmers to undertake sustainable farming practices.

Suggestions

1. Higher prices should be determined by the government for organic produce rather than conventional produce. Assurance of a high price for organic crops will give an impetus to the farmers to adopt sustainable agriculture.
2. Timely and quick release of allotted funds for sustainable agricultural development must be ensured by the state governments removing all lags which will increase the adoption rate of sustainable agriculture among the small and marginal farmers.
3. The agricultural universities/research institution must put a sincere effort at their respective level to encourage research activities in the field of sustainable agricultural practices.

4. The government, NGO's, Civil societies etc. must organize various training sessions, workshops, seminars on sustainable farming with the help of specialist's resource persons for farmers.
5. The private companies should be encouraged in organic crops production by government.
6. On our individual level we can promote organic products by going for say organic farming in our home garden, buying organic products from the market etc.

Conclusion:

Sustainable agriculture has a host of benefits to offer and if executed properly it has full potential to be a precious part of Indian agriculture. While states like Sikkim and Andhra Pradesh are leading the way on sustainable agriculture in India; its adoption remains very meager at an all India level. As per data of Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers welfare only about 2.30 million hectares of farmland of the 140.1 million hectares of net sown area of the country was under organic cultivation as of 2019. The Government should undertake sincere efforts to encourage sustainable agriculture by making adequate budgetary allocations towards sustainable farming, building a bridge of knowledge between farmer and his way of farming, provide an assurance of high price for organic produce to the farmers. Implementing these initiatives at a larger scale and in a better organized way will lead to development of Atmanirbhar Krishi (Self reliant agriculture) and ultimately the long-cherished dream of Atmanirbhar Bharat or a Self-reliant India; a happy and progressive New India of the 21st century would be a reality.

Endnotes

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